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D5.1 Stakeholder Engagement Mid Term Report

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EU-CON	Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	
EU-SEC	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Effective stakeholder engagement is the pillar to any Coordination and Support Action project. This deliverable showcases the efforts conducted by the StandICT.eu 2026 consortium to expand the project's community base during the first half of its running.

Building from the work done throughout the first two iterations of the project, it was able to further extend its links with three specific stakeholder groups identified as critical from the start of the project, and for which new project partners (DIGITAL SME, Fraunhofer, and Open Forum Europe) were included to StandICT.eu 2026's consortium (in addition to existing partners Trust-IT, Dublin City University, and AUSTRALO):

- **SMEs (225+ directly engaged stakeholders, and 1640+ indirectly and via other SME multipliers by M17);**
- **The academic and research community (630+);**
- **The open-source community (180+).**

Additionally, **12 different European or international standardisation organisations and 6 NSBs were directly engaged**, as well as **policymakers from 3 core European Commission Directorate Generals**. Last, **16 new collaborations were established with ICT standardisation-related Horizon Europe projects**, either through Memorandums of Understanding or cross-project cooperation and information sharing.

To do so, StandICT.eu 2026 expanded some of its previous engagement channels which had been crafted through previous iterations of the project. Such channels under StandICT.eu 2026 are broadly of four main categories:

- **StandICT.eu 2026's Open Calls process, and its platform** centralising all of the project's services - with 53500 users having visited it by M17, and 107 funded fellows by Open Call 3;
- **Participatory engagement** means, of which bodies and processes such as the Forum on European Strategy for ICT Standards (FOREST) and stakeholder consultations were added to the last iterations of the project;
- **Events** of different natures, with notably a strong focus on trainings under StandICT.eu 2026 as compared to previous iterations, which amounted to a total of 1296 engaged registrants across 12 different events in the first 17 months;
- **Communication outreach**, via social media outlets, publications, and newsletters.

As the consortium now looks on to the second half of the project's tenure, one of its key aims will be to better profile the different engaged stakeholders, notably those engaged via events. This will enable to map out an even more accurate picture of the StandICT.eu 2026 community - ever growing, and across an increasing amount of stakeholder categories.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AIOTI	Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation
UNE	Asociación Española de Normalización
VDE	Association for Electrical, Electronic & Information Technologies
AFNOR	Association Française de Normalisation
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
BSI	British Standards Institute
DIN	Deutsches Institut Für Normung
DG CNECT	Directorate General for Communications Network, Content and Technology
DG GROW	Directorate General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs
DG RTD	Directorate General for Research and Innovation
UNI	Ente Italiano de Normazione
EURAS	European Academy for Standardisation
CEN-CENELEC	European Committee for Standardisation and Electrotechnical Standardisation
APELL	European Open Source Software Business Association
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EAG	External Advisory Group
EPE	External Pool of Evaluators
FOREST	Forum on European Strategy for ICT Standards
HLF	High-Level Forum on Standardisation
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
INATBA	International Association for Trusted Blockchain Applications
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
ITU	International Telecommunications Union
JTC	Joint Technical Committee
VDMA	Machinery and Equipment Manufacturers Association
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NSB	National Standard Body
OASC	Open and Agile Smart Cities
OC	Open Call
OFE	Open Forum Europe
OASIS	Organisation for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards
SESEC	Seconded European Standardisation Expert in China
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SBS	Small Business Standards
SDO	Standard Developing Organisation
TWG	Technical Working Group
3GPP	Third Generation Partnership Project

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and Scope

StandICT.eu 2026's core objective is to bolster the European ICT standardisation ecosystem, ensuring its positioning in global standardisation dynamics. It does so by not only supporting European experts financially (with 2 925 000 € in funding earmarked over 36 months, through a series of 9 Open Calls), enabling them to engage in crucial work at technical level, but also through a series of adjacent initiatives buttressing the overall ecosystem: trainings, monitoring of standardisation developments, and general recommendation work.

As such, stakeholder engagement - in its broadest sense - lies at the centre of StandICT.eu's prerogatives. The project cannot count solely on the engagement of long-time engaged ICT standardisation experts: the European Union needs to replenish its pool of experts, reach out to new target audiences, if it wishes to maintain a central global standing. This is namely why StandICT.eu 2026, in its new iteration of a now well-established project, expanded its consortia (Trust-IT, AUSTRALO, and Dublin City University) to new partners:

- The European DIGITAL SME Alliance (DIGITAL SME), largest network of ICT small and medium enterprises, with more than 45 000 members across Europe;
- Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft (Fraunhofer), based in Germany and the world's leading applied research organisation;
- Open Foundation Europe (OFE), a not-for-profit think-tank focused on explaining the merits of openness in computing to policy makers and communities across Europe.

The aim was, in line with EU priorities in the realm of ICT standardisation, to better outreach to new communities in the European ICT standardisation landscape: small and medium enterprises (SMEs), research & education communities, and the open-source communities.

This Stakeholder Engagement Mid Term Report is reflective of this shift. While maintaining a broader overview of the different engagement activities across these first 17 months - many of which benefit from the project's many years of operation, and accumulated network, this Report also showcases the project's transitioning towards the effective engagement of these new communities.

1.2 Structure

The Report reads as follows:

- **Chapter 1** serves as an introduction to the document, presenting its scope, structure & relation with the project's other deliverables;
- **Chapter 2** presents the followed methodology of the project's stakeholder engagement activities;
- **Chapter 3** expands upon the various engagement channels operationalised by the project to engage the widest possible and most relevant community around StandICT.eu 2026. This chapter also provides updates on the communication channels used and the results achieved up to M17, in line with the Communications Plan.

Communications results are presented in this deliverable because they are strictly connected to engagement actions, but also because no other official deliverables are due for updating communication activities at this stage.

- **Chapter 4** presents a state of play of the engaged ecosystem at M17, focusing on the effective synergies and results;
- **Chapter 5** offers some preliminary conclusions and learnt lessons from this first half of the project's stakeholder engagement activities, serving as a basis for a renewed and enhanced process for the project's latter phase.

1.3 Relation with other project deliverables

This Mid Term Report will be updated at M36, at the closure of the project, to accommodate subsequent stakeholder engagement activities that will have taken place after M17. It should also be taken into close consideration with a series of other related project deliverables, which may provide more details on specific dimensions of StandICT.eu's broader stakeholder engagement activities. In particular:

- D2.2 (Stakeholder Consultation Process - Mid-term Report) and D2.3 (Stakeholder Consultation Process - Final Report) provide a comprehensive summary of StandICT.eu's stakeholder consultation processes, some of which will be briefly presented below in this Report;
- D3.1 (Call Monitoring 1), D3.2 (Call Monitoring 2) and D3.4 (Call Monitoring 3) cover the outcome of the submissions of the different Open Calls and the External Pool of Evaluators (EPE) selection, which constitute a significant dimension of StandICT.eu's stakeholder engagement;
- D4.1 (Standardisation Training Strategy) offers a targeted strategy for outreaching to different stakeholder groups with tailored trainings on ICT standardisation-related topics;
- D4.2 (Interim Report on Education in Standardisation) and D4.3 (Final Report on Education in Standardisation) address the impact of these training activities to the various stakeholder groups;
- D6.1 (Plan for Communication & Stakeholder Engagement Strategy & Plan for Promotion of the Open Call) provides the project's initial strategy to be followed regarding stakeholder engagement;
- D6.4 (Monitoring and contributing to sensitive issues in ICT standardisation) reports on specific events and engagement actions organised by the consortium under the FOREST remit. These activities aim to discuss and raise awareness about sensitive topics such as the role of women and gender bias in ICT standardisation and the link between Human Rights and ICT standardisation to facilitate these important conversations and promoting inclusivity and ethical considerations within the ICT standardisation community.

2. METHODOLOGY

Chapter 2 outlines the methodology behind StandICT.eu 2026's stakeholder engagement. Section 1 presents the ecosystem building approach, a four-fold sequence which makes use of various engagement channels to attract an increasing number of parties into the project's activities. A second section goes in depth into the seven identified stakeholder groups. A final section closes with the allocation of responsibilities among the project consortia towards the engagement of the different targeted communities.

2.1 Ecosystem Building Approach

At the centre of StandICT.eu 2026's ecosystem is its online platform¹. Similarly to previous iterations of the project and having progressively added on features favouring a better engagement with different stakeholders, it acts as a focal point by delivering all the project's core services. The ecosystem building approach follows a four-fold sequence:

- **Monitor standardisation work and train prospective standardisation experts**, through Technical Working Groups, the EU Observatory for ICT Standardisation, and the Standards Academy;
- **Support and promote** European standardisation experts' work, through the Fellowship Programme, priorly evaluated by an External Pool of Experts, and whose results are further disseminated through both workshops and webinars, and the project's External Advisory Group;
- **Engage stakeholders** in the process, for them to both participate as standardisation experts and raise awareness on the project's results to better communicate on the benefits of ICT standardisation;
- **Serve broader European interests**, notably through the project's Forum for European Strategy on ICT Standards (FOREST) providing an early warning mechanism to inform policymakers of critical standardisation developments at technical committee level, and by establishing pan-European synergies with other relevant stakeholders.

The sequence naturally feeds into each respective step, as shown in Figure 1 below. Stakeholder engagement - in the stricter sense - is thereby at the heart of a comprehensive methodology, and cannot be understood in silo from the sequence's other components. Each strand of StandICT.eu 2026's work is reflective of a continuous attempt to engage as many people as possible into the project - whether through trainings, research work, or the actual financial support offered to fellows working at technical committee level.

As apparent in the figure, seven main stakeholder groups are targeted in the project's engagement. The next section goes into them in more detail.

¹ <https://www.standict.eu/>

FIGURE 1 - FIGURE 1 - STANDICT.EU 2026'S ECOSYSTEM BUILDING APPROACH

2.2 Identification of the Target Groups

Seven core stakeholder groups were identified:

- ICT standardisation experts;
- Companies, SMEs & other industry players;
- Standards bodies;
- Academics, trainers & other experts in education;
- Policymakers;
- Horizon Europe and Digital Europe Programme projects involved in ICT standardisation;
- The general public.

The following subsections expand upon each, outlining the specific rational and engagement objectives, as well as providing some examples of key actors to outreach for each stakeholder group.

■ 2.2.1 ICT STANDARDISATION EXPERTS

The first target group of critical importance to the StandICT.eu 2026 project is the current pool of European ICT standardisation experts. Such experts may sit in various Technical Committees, at both European and international levels, working first-handedly on ICT-centred topics.

Yet, in some cases, there can exist a relative lack of alignment between the technical work being carried out on the one hand, and broader European priorities on the other. This is a hindrance for the European standardisation ecosystem - most and foremost at international level, where the number of European experts with leading positions (chairs, convenors, project leaders) is relatively low as compared to larger countries such as the United States or China. As put by Santiago Tenorio in April 2022, director of Network Architecture at Vodafone: "the weight of Europe in standardisation bodies has been eroded by the growth of American and

Asian companies that have deeper pockets to invest in trying to influence the technical discussions². The more recent rise of Chinese influence in international standardisation has been extensively covered in the literature, and sheds a particular light on this trend - further reference can, notably, be found in a comprehensive March 2020 paper by the Heinrich Böll Foundation³.

The objective for StandICT.eu 2026 is thereby to be able to become a focal point of reference for this community of European experts, and channel their work at technical level towards policy outputs of use to European policymakers - at both European and international levels. This is devised through different means, which will be better expanded upon in Chapter 3 of this Report.

■ 2.2.2 COMPANIES, SMES & OTHER INDUSTRY PLAYERS

Companies (with a particular focus on SMEs) and other important industry players (such as industry associations) are a second important target group for the StandICT.eu 2026 project.

While larger companies tend to have more access and influence in standardisation bodies' technical committees, SMEs have been identified under the new iteration of the StandICT.eu project as a critical target audience to dedicate particular efforts to. Whether due to lack of resources, knowledge, or time, SMEs often remain outside of standardisation developments. Yet, with them representing 99% of all businesses across the European Union⁴, this poses serious issues of standard suitability. Without adequate participation in standardisation processes, European companies risk having to cope with overly expensive standards, which are difficult to implement. StandICT.eu 2026 strives to alleviate this gap, attracting smaller players into standardisation work - notably through deeper trainings and awareness-raising efforts. Beyond the direct participation of the European DIGITAL SME Alliance in StandICT.eu 2026 as consortium partner, other relevant organisations to outreach to in this regard are Small Business Standards (SBS), the Annex III organisation representing SMEs in European standardisation, and SMEunited.

More specific industry players are also targeted. These may, for instance, be topic related. Wide membership-based industry associations are strategic to align with in that regard; not only for the topical expertise they may be able to bring on a particular matter, but more broadly for the capacity to better align standardisation and business concerns. Industry associations such as the International Association for Trusted Blockchain Applications (INATBA), for blockchain, the European Cybersecurity Organisation (ECISO), for cybersecurity-related matters, Open and Agile Smart Cities (OASC), for the field of smart cities, or the Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation (AIOTI), for IoT concerns, are some of the relevant examples to be mentioned here.

Last, a particular focus is taken in StandICT.eu 2026 to expand its attention to open-source communities. The ICT standardisation landscape is not the same as when StandICT.eu first initiated as a project, in 2018. Some standards are maintained as open-source, such as APIs, or specific interfaces and protocols. While the European Commission's 2022 Standardisation

² <https://www.euractiv.com/section/digital/news/the-risk-of-fragmentation-for-international-standards/>

³ <https://www.ui.se/globalassets/ui.se-eng/publications/other-publications/technical-standardisation-china-and-the-future-international-order.pdf>

⁴ https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/smes/sme-definition_en

Strategy acknowledged this shift, calling for European SDOs to better integrate open-source solutions into their activities⁵, StandICT.eu 2026 attempts to further bridge this gap in its outreach activities. While this is widely aided by the addition of Open Forum Europe as project partner to the new consortium, other relevant organisations such as the European Open Source Software Business Association (APELL) or the Apache Software Foundation are some of the important target organisations within this realm.

■ 2.2.3 STANDARDS BODIES

Considering the project's primal focus on attracting European standardisation experts to its platform, it is essential for StandICT.eu 2026 to entertain fruitful relations with the standards bodies in which said experts operate and to spread the different activities of the project.

The standards bodies of interest in the ICT-realm are both European and international. At European level, the three recognised European Standards Bodies (CEN, CENELEC, and ETSI) are paramount. Particular attention to certain Technical Committees, in line with regularly incoming new EU priorities, is to be put: the recent case of the Digital Product Passport, with respective work at both CEN-CENELEC's JTC24 and ETSI's Environmental Engineering Technical Committee, is a good reflection of that. At national level of the European standardisation system too, maintaining relations with National Standards Bodies (NSBs) is equally of importance. Through the national delegation principle, these cannot be neglected - and organisations such as DIN (Germany), AFNOR (France), UNE (Spain), or UNI (Italy) adequately engaged with.

At international level, a number of relevant standardisation bodies can be mentioned: the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO), the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), the International Telecommunications Union (ITU), the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), the Organisation for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards (OASIS), etc. As for the European level, significant technological developments and creations of new Technical Committees should be closely monitored, and aligned upon. A relevant and recent example of this is the creation of a new Focus Group Metaverse (FG-MV) by ITU, in 2023⁶.

■ 2.2.4 ACADEMICS, TRAINERS & OTHER EXPERTS IN EDUCATION

Fourth, StandICT.eu 2026 takes a particular stance on consolidating synergies with - and between - standardisation's academic sphere. While some efforts had already initiated in the StandICT.eu 2023 with the creation of the first version of the Standards Academy⁷, more should be done.

As recognised by the European Commission in 2022, there is a "generational shift"⁸ when it comes to standardisation expertise in Europe. The European standardisation pool of experts is ageing, with limited engagement of younger profiles. Very little formal education programmes

⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/48598>

⁶ <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/focusgroups/mv/Pages/default.aspx>

⁷ <https://www.standict.eu/euos-academy>

⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/QANDA_22_662

on standardisation exist, and neither do vocational training programs. In parallel, the landscape of standardisation is expanding to new complex topics with need of expertise. The ICT field is particularly concerned by this trend, with nascent standardisation areas in regards for instance to artificial intelligence, data interoperability, or more recently still quantum computing - as highlighted in the European Commission's 2024 Annual Union Work Programme on European Standardisation, with quantum technologies topping the policy priorities⁹.

Addressing this, one of StandICT.eu 2026's core objectives is to consolidate links with academia and other relevant standards education initiatives. These include, for instance, the European Academy for Standardisation (EURAS¹⁰), or the recently-launched Edu4Standards¹¹ European project which aims to significantly bolster European standardisation education efforts by 2027. Alignment with the European Commission's High-Level Forum on Standardisation¹², and more particularly its Workstream 1 on Education, is also a major target. Overall, StandICT.eu 2026's efforts in that regard are to be considerably supported by the presence in the consortia of Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft, one of the leading standardisation research centres at global level.

■ 2.2.5 POLICYMAKERS

Referring to the fourth step of the ecosystem building approach presented in the first section of this chapter, alignment with European policymakers is essential. Whether to communicate important results or trends to them, or take on new recommendations, StandICT.eu 2026 has a need to be in regular contact with key departments of the European Commission.

The most relevant departments in that regard are DG CNECT (Communications Network, Content and Technology) and DG GROW (Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs):

- DG CNECT leads the European Commission's work on ICT matters, making it a central counterpart to StandICT.eu 2026. While it has a specific unit with a team centred on transversal standardisation matters (CNECT D3), other technology-based units (such as CNECT A2, on artificial intelligence, or CNECT H2 on cybersecurity) are also important contact points to be nurtured. DG CNECT also coordinates the Multi-Stakeholder Platform on ICT Standardisation, and its various Task Forces such as the Task Force Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation.
- DG GROW leads the European Commission's work on broader standardisation matters. It notably has a Chief Standardisation Officer, in the person of Deputy Director-General Maive Rute. Its unit GROW H3 focuses on standards policy, and coordinates the European Commission's High-Level Forum on Standardisation.

⁹ https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/news/commission-publishes-its-annual-union-work-programme-european-standardisation-2024-2024-02-02_en

¹⁰ <https://www.euras.org/>

¹¹ <https://edu4standards.eu/>

¹² https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/european-standards/standardisation-policy/high-level-forum-european-standardisation_en

Other European Commission departments, such as DG DIGIT (Digital Services) or DG RTD (Research & Innovation) may also be of interest for specific activities - for instance linked to the training component of the project.

■ 2.2.6 HORIZON EUROPE AND DIGITAL EUROPE PROGRAMME PROJECTS INVOLVED IN ICT STANDARDISATION

A large number of European ICT-related Research & Innovation (R&I) projects contribute, in various degrees, to standardisation work. These are generally funded under the Horizon Europe or Digital Europe Programmes. As such, it is important for StandICT.eu 2026 to monitor the landscape of these projects and find as many synergies as possible in order to leverage the impact of other ongoing standardisation efforts elsewhere.

Partner projects can benefit from StandICT.eu 2026's established tools and resources on ICT standardisation, useful for their own research work. On the other hand, these projects can increase the visibility of StandICT.eu 2026's Open Calls, attracting new potential experts from different verticals to the platform. Such projects include, *inter alia*:

- The AI Data and Robotics Association¹³, a coordination and support action aimed at ensuring the success of the AI, Data and Robotics Partnership set up by the European Commission;
- BlockStand¹⁴ and SEEBLOCKS¹⁵, two Digital Europe Programme projects supporting blockchain standardisation efforts in Europe;
- NGI Sargasso¹⁶, a project centred around new generation internet technologies;
- The 6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association (6G-IA¹⁷), working to contribute to Europe's leadership on 5G and 6G research;
- The AI-On Demand Platform¹⁸, a community-driven channel designed to empower European research and innovation in artificial intelligence.

■ 2.2.7 GENERAL PUBLIC

Last, StandICT.eu's stakeholder engagement efforts need to more generally embrace the general public. To the average European citizen, standardisation is an obscure concept. Yet standards are the spine of a healthy and competitive European economy. In the ICT sector in particular, core technologies (such as mobile communications, data transfers, or video streaming) are robust only thanks to underlying standards.

This is why StandICT.eu 2026 strives to raise general awareness among European citizens. Through webinars, training activities, or various communications (newsletters, participation to events, etc.), it can contribute to driving ICT standardisation matters up the public debate.

¹³ <https://adr-association.eu/>

¹⁴ <https://blockstand.eu/>

¹⁵ <https://seeblocks.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://ngisargasso.eu/>

¹⁷ <https://6g-ia.eu/>

¹⁸ <https://www.ai4europe.eu/>

2.3 Engagement Strategy of the Stakeholder Groups

StandICT.eu 2026’s consortium undertakes its activities through monthly Work Package meetings. From an early stage, it was decided to organise joint Work Package 5 (Stakeholder Engagement - led by DIGITAL SME) and 6 (Communication & Dissemination - led by Trust-IT) meetings in reason of the close synergies between the two strands of work.

In May 2023, an Action Plan was decided upon by the partners. It laid out the main steps to be carried out by the respective Work Package 5 partners, as well as an allocation of responsibilities regarding the engagement of the seven forementioned stakeholder groups.

The following figure summarises the main agreed outreach dynamics. Due to the new composition of the consortium, and the addition of three new partners in StandICT.eu 2026 each covering different target groups (namely, Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft for the Academic community - SG4, DIGITAL SME for SMEs, and Open Forum Europe for the Open Source community - both under SG2), responsibilities were able to be clearly defined building on the added-value of each respective partner.

Nonetheless, in many cases different partners tended to provide additional support to each other due to intrinsic relationships with various contacts across stakeholder groups.

FIGURE 2 - STANDICT.EU 2026'S OUTREACH DYNAMICS

3. ENGAGEMENT CHANNELS

This Chapter goes through the various engagement channels used by the StandICT.eu 2026 consortia to effectively outreach to the different identified stakeholder groups in Chapter 2. Such channels can be summed up into four macro categories:

- **StandICT.eu 2026's Open Calls & Platform**, the former of which four Open Calls were conducted during these first 17 months;
- **Participatory engagement**, through project items such as the Expert Advisory Group, the External Pool of Evaluators, the EU Observatory for ICT Standardisation & its Technical Working Groups, the Forum on European Strategy for ICT Standards (FOREST), and the project's stakeholder consultations;
- **Events**, whether webinars, Standards Academy trainings, SME leadership workshops, or third-party events;
- **Communication outreach**, essentially through social media, publications & reports, and newsletters & press releases.

3.1 StandICT.eu2026 Open Calls & Platform

■ 3.1.1 OPEN CALLS

StandICT.eu 2026's series of Open Calls are one of the key channels to engage with the ICT standardisation community. The StandICT.eu 2026 fellowship programme runs from January 2023 until December 2025, and provides 2 925 000 € in total funding for the participation of European standardisation specialists in key European and international SDOs.

Topics were encouraged based on the European Commission's Multi-Stakeholder Platform's most recent Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation. However, through alignment with policymakers, StandICT.eu 2026 was able to highlight critical topics to be highly encouraged in each call. For instance, in the first four calls the topics of Virtual Worlds and of the Digital Product Passport were particularly sought after.

Each open call is accompanied with a new visual, putting in the spotlight a relevant quote by a high-level European policymaker on the importance of standardisation. Figure 3 shows the specific examples of Open Calls 2 and 3, with respective quotes from Maive Rute (European Commission Chief Standardisation Officer) and Iliana Ivanova (European Commissioner for Innovation, Research, Culture, Education and Youth).

By M17, **four of the nine Open Calls have been completed** (Table 1). 60 days were given between the publication of the call and its closure, with wide dissemination efforts by consortium partners across their networks. Specific results and outcomes of these calls, with precise data, will be further presented in Chapter 4.

FIGURE 3 - EXAMPLES OF OPEN CALL PROMOTIONAL BANNERS

Open Calls	Deadline
OC1	10 July 2023
OC2	2 October 2023
OC3	9 January 2024
OC4	12 April 2024

TABLE 1 - STANDICT.EU 2026'S OPEN CALLS BY M17

■ 3.1.2 STANDICT.EU 2026 PLATFORM

The StandICT.eu 2026 platform centralises all of the project's key services, as well as presents in a clear way the objectives of the project. As such, it is one of the most important engagement channels with all of the different stakeholder groups getting to come across the project's activities.

In particular, it is the gateway to both the EU Observatory for ICT Standardisation (to access the online standards repository and the Technical Working Groups) and the TRUST-GRANTS Platform (to submit applications to the Open Calls and to manage the different fellowships). All of the project's documents and publications can also be found, as well as the different upcoming training initiatives and events.

In October 2023, the homepage of the website was refreshed with a new visual identity. Figure 4 shows a capture of this new visual identity, which aims to be more appealing to the user - and in particular the general public, which more than for the other identified stakeholder groups needs to be specifically enticed to remain on the platform and navigate across different pages. Work is ongoing to adapt this new visual identity to the other pages of the website, and better display some of them to make them more engaging to the different users.

FIGURE 4 - STANDICT.EU 2026'S PLATFORM'S NEW VISUAL IDENTITY

19,496 users who accepted the analytics cookies visited www.standict.eu since StandICT.eu 2026 has started (in the timeframe M1-M17 - last tracking on 29 May 2024). Since the current acceptance rate is about 36.4%, it is possible to assume that **about 53.5 thousand users visited the website in M1-M17.**

FIGURE 5 - STANDICT.EU 2026'S WEBSITE TRAFFIC DATA ANALYTICS

The number of sessions per user (1.95) is also satisfactory. The number of sessions per user is the average number of times a person visits a website per month. It is a critical metric because it shows how engaged your users are with your website. A high number of sessions per user means that people are engaged with a website and keep coming back for more. The average number of sessions per user is 1.4. Based on this, a good number of sessions per user is anything above 1.6. A decent proportion of users returning to another session means that the online content is attractive.

The bounce rate is also in line with the expectations. It represents the percentage of users who enter the site and then leave ("bounce") rather than continuing to view other pages within the same site. A bounce rate of 40% or lower is considered good.

Last, Figure 6 and Table 2 respectively show the geographical coverage of the users of the StandICT.eu 2026 platform, and the most consulted pages.

FIGURE 6 - STANDICT.EU 2026'S WEBSITE TRAFFIC DATA ANALYTICS - GEOGRAPHICAL COVERAGE WITH TOP 5 COUNTRIES BY NUMBER OF USERS

Page title	Views
Home StandICT.eu 2026	7668
A Landscape of Standards for the Digital Product Passport (EUOS TWG) StandICT.eu 2026	1953
Landscape of Digital Product Passport Standards StandICT.eu 2026	1538

StandICT.eu 2026 - 3rd Open Call StandICT.eu 2026	1632
StandICT 2026 Call for Evaluators StandICT.eu 2026	1439
Standards Repository StandICT.eu 2026	2096
StandICT.eu 2026 - 1st Open Call StandICT.eu 2026	1177
EUOS StandICT.eu 2026	1248
StandICT.eu 2026 - 4th Open Call StandICT.eu 2026	1225
StandICT.eu 2026 - 2nd Open Call StandICT.eu 2026	1023

TABLE 2 - STANDICT.EU 2026'S WEBSITE TRAFFIC DATA ANALYTICS - TOP 10 VIEWED PAGES

3.2 Participatory Engagement

Due to its nature as a Coordination and Support Action project, co-funded by the European Commission, StandICT.eu 2026 bases an essential part of its stakeholder outreach through *participatory engagement*. The different identified stakeholder groups are first-handedly engaged into the project, through direct participation in specific activities. The following subsections outline the different channels falling under this category of engagement:

- The Expert Advisory Group;
- The External Pool of Evaluators;
- The EU Observatory for ICT Standardisation (EUOS) & Technical Working Groups;
- The Forum on European Strategy for ICT Standards (FOREST);
- The project's stakeholder consultations.

■ 3.2.1 EXPERT ADVISORY GROUP

One of the most important of these forms of participatory engagement is via StandICT.eu 2026's External Advisory Group (EAG). The EAG is an advisory body to the project, **composed of 10 high-level standardisation experts** (Table 3). It is set up in a supportive capacity to guide, monitor and prioritise its strategic direction. It contributes to identifying strategic standardisation priorities and existing challenges, as well as to policy documents published by the StandICT.eu 2026 consortium.

Beyond, EAG members are expected to disseminate the results and key messages of StandICT.eu 2026 across their network. Due to their high-level roles, this is viewed as a highly effective tactic for wider stakeholder engagement of the StandICT.eu brand.

EAG Member	Affiliation
Ana Garcia Robles	Big Data Value Association (BDVA) - Secretary General
Betty Xu	Seconded European Standardisation Expert in China Project (SESEC) - Director
Diana Dus	European Business School of Standards - Stakeholder Specialist
Karl Gruen	Austrian Standards - Director
Lindsay Frost	Chief Standardisation Engineer - NEC Laboratories Europe
Martin Chapman	Independent Consultant on EU Technical Policy & Standardisation
Sandra Drechsler	VDMA - Managing Director Technical Affairs & Standardisation
Sebastian Hallensbelen	VDE - Head of Digitalisation and AI
Silona Bonewald	IEEE SA OPEN - Executive Director
Stephan Weisgerber	DIN - Head of Digital Platforms

TABLE 3 - COMPOSITION OF THE EXTERNAL ADVISORY GROUP BY M17

Terms of Reference for the EAG were prepared in May 2023. **Six different meetings were organised** since then, chaired by Dublin City University (Table 4).

EAG Calls	Date
EAG Call 1	5 May 2023
EAG Call 2	7 July 2023
EAG Call 3	1 September 2023
EAG Call 4	3 November 2023
EAG Call 5	26 January 2024
EAG Call 6	8 April 2024

TABLE 4 - EXTERNAL ADVISORY GROUP MEETINGS BY M17

■ 3.2.2 EXTERNAL POOL OF EVALUATORS

The second key channel for StandICT.eu 2026 to engage with different stakeholders from relevant standardisation backgrounds is through its External Pool of Evaluators (EPE).

EPE members are tasked to review the proposals to the StandICT.eu Fellowship Programme. They ensure an impartial, transparent and consistent review process. Upon closure of each Open Call, three members are drawn from the EPE pool to evaluate each eligible application - effectively engaging a high number of Evaluators for each call.

An Open Call for the External Pool of Evaluators was launched early 2023, closing on 31 May 2023. The call was widely disseminated by each partner, and **50+ members from various backgrounds were ultimately selected**. Figure 7 shows the promotional material used for the occasion. In the Spring of 2024, a second call for Evaluators was opened, **scoring over 20 new applications**.

This engagement channel is considered pertinent due to the wide outreach it generated in a first phase through the dissemination phase of the Open Call, and then to the regular engagement of the EPE members with StandICT.eu 2026 Fellows during their evaluations. Further, this allows high-level standardisation experts to keep engaging and monitoring the variety of work proposals submitted by other European experts applying to the Fellowship Open Calls, consolidating an overall European ecosystem.

FIGURE 7 - EXTERNAL POOL OF EVALUATORS OPEN CALL PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL

■ 3.2.3 EU OBSERVATORY FOR ICT STANDARDISATION & TECHNICAL WORKING GROUPS

StandICT.eu 2026's EU Observatory for ICT Standardisation is the project's third important channel for participatory engagement. Through various Technical Working Groups (TWGs), it empowers the contributions from the various funded Fellows of the StandICT.eu network.

These Technical Working Groups lead to the publishing of various reports, namely Landscape Analysis Reports. At mid-project, **StandICT.eu 2026 has published (or soon to be) four reports:**

- A Landscape Report on Digital Product Passport standards (March 2023)¹⁹, with over 200 standards referenced;
- A Landscape Report of Ontologies standards (May 2023)²⁰, presenting a set of carefully curated ontologies based on their relevance to the ICT sector and their various maturity levels;
- A Landscape Report on CitiVerse standardisation (December 2023)²¹, focusing on standards to consider when constructing a CitiVerse and its different application areas;
- A Gap Analysis Report on Internet of Things and one on edge computing standardisation are being finalised at the moment of writing this deliverable. They define and identify key IoT and edge computing standardisation gaps in several initiatives, as support for the work being done by relevant SDOs on the matter.

These reports directly serve the needs of the European standardisation ecosystem, and identify critical priorities. For instance, the Technical Working Group on the CitiVerse was formed to support the European Commission's efforts and engagement in ITU-T's newly established Focus Group Metaverse, in Q3 2023. Similarly the Landscape Report on Digital Product Passport standards was created in support of the European Commission's Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation, initially proposed in 2022.

Other Technical Working Groups are now in the making, following critical developments and standardisation trends.

FIGURE 8 - EXAMPLE OF TWG PUBLICATIONS

¹⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/7728381>

²⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/7907025>

²¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/10262579>

■ 3.2.4 FOREST

StandICT.eu 2026's Forum on European Strategy for ICT Standards (FOREST) is the project's body that ensures that the experts' resources are well-steered towards the European Commission's goals, notably by monitoring sensitive issues identified by the StandICT.eu fellows. It also seeks collaboration with other EU-funded initiatives focused on standards.

FOREST is composed of **8 members**. A kick-off meeting was organised in May 2024, with members stemming from various SDOs and covering different ICT priorities, as well as the different project partners. Table 5 provides a synthetic overview of the members of the group (excluding the StandICT.eu 2026 project partners).

A first early warning system report, summarising the sensitive issues identified among the fellows, was delivered to the European Commission in May 2024. Periodic updates are now expected, to continue in the same direction.

In sum, this channel enables to keep engagement levels of StandICT.eu 2026's fellows at a high level, linking their technical work to policy and strategic considerations. Beyond, it provides a focal point for high-level experts in the ICT standardisation scene to align and support the European Commission's work.

FOREST Member	Affiliation
Christian Grafenauer	Standards Expert
Dave Lewis	Trinity College Dublin
Diana Soeiro	Portuguese Business Ethics Association (APEE)
Lindsay Frost	NEC Laboratories Europe
Panos Kudumakis	Head of UK Delegation (ISO/IEC JTC1/SC29)
Philip Maurer	CEN/CENELEC
Sandra Feliciano	Polytechnic Institute of Porto
Viveka Bonde	Bonde Advokater

TABLE 5 - LIST OF FOREST MEMBERS

■ 3.2.5 STAKEHOLDER CONSULTATIONS

StandICT.eu 2026's fifth and last key means of participatory engagement is through stakeholder consultations.

This process, new to the 2026 edition of the project, aims to ensure that StandICT.eu 2026's positioning is well aligned with other European initiatives and important stakeholders. In practice, policy-related deliverables of the StandICT.eu project are to be consulted upon with external parties. By doing so, two main objectives are attained:

- A large variety of stakeholders are outreached to, and kept informed of StandICT.eu 2026's work and initiatives;
- The reports under consultation are bolstered by additional lines of comments and suggestions, coming from experts in the field.

Terms of Reference for the Stakeholder Consultation Process were defined in Q2-Q3 2023, outlining the modalities of the process. After review by the External Advisory Group, they were finally approved in December 2023. At time of writing, **a first large consultation is underway for StandICT.eu 2026's D2.1**. Titled "Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape", it identifies key challenges and trends for Europe to face, and provides preliminary recommendations. Consulted parties include project partners' internal organisations and (where relevant) memberships, the members of the External Advisory Group, of FOREST, and of the different organisations with which StandICT.eu 2026 holds Memorandums of Understanding (MoUs).

More details on this process will be outlined in a separate deliverable (D2.2). However, due to its close linkage to stakeholder engagement activities, it nonetheless warrants attention in this report.

3.3 Events

StandICT.eu 2026's events are one of the most important ways it engages with the broad stakeholder community - and in particular the general public (SG7). These events may be of different nature, based on the target audience or expected result. They can be broken down to four main subcategories:

- Webinars, on a wide range of topics and appealing to virtually any stakeholder group;
- Standards Academy Trainings, aimed at stakeholders looking to improve their knowledge of the ICT standardisation ecosystem;
- SME Leadership Workshops, specifically aimed at SMEs looking to improve their capacity to lead work in standards bodies' technical committees;
- Third-party events, which StandICT.eu 2026 partners participate in directly or simply cross-reference for the benefit of the broader ICT standardisation stakeholder community.

The below subsections expand in more detail upon each. In total, StandICT.eu 2026 **organised 12 events of various natures by M17, amounting to 1296 registrations and directly engaged stakeholders, while also participating in or cross-referencing 12 other relevant ICT standardisation-related third-party events.**

■ 3.3.1 WEBINARS

Webinars are the first of these kinds of events. Table 6 presents the different webinars organised by M17, including registration numbers. In total, **5 webinars were organised, amounting to 654 registrations.** These exclude the Standards Academy Trainings, SME

Leadership Workshops and third-party events - which will be presented in subsequent subsections.

Figure 9 gives an example of a typical webinar promotional banner, displayed on StandICT.eu 2026's website in the Events section, and widely disseminated on social media.

Webinar	Date	Registrations
Walk & Talk Webinar: Digital Product Passport ²²	28 April 2023	212
Women in ICT Standards - Second Edition ²³	4 July 2023	81
Walk & Talk: Navigating the Citiverse ²⁴	24 October 2023	108
OFE Lounge 2024: Standardisation and Open Source in the Age of Software Regulation ²⁵	22 February 2024 - Kick Off 29 February 2024 - AI Act 7 March 2024 - Cyber Resilience Act 14 March 2024 - Legal Challenges and Innovation 3 April 2024 - Final Workshop	172
Women in ICT Standards - Third Edition ²⁶	7 March 2024	81

TABLE 6 - LIST OF ORGANISED WEBINARS BY M17

²² <https://www.standict.eu/digital/priduct/passport/webinar>

²³ <https://www.standict.eu/events/webinar-women-ict-standards-focus-gender-gap-ict-standardisation-and-standards>

²⁴ <https://www.standict.eu/events/walk-talk-webinar-towards-citiverse-citizen-centric-virtual-world-eu-cities-and-communities>

²⁵ <https://www.standict.eu/events/ofe-lounge-2024-standardisation-and-open-source-age-software-regulation>

²⁶ <https://www.standict.eu/events/webinar-women-ict-standards-3>

FIGURE 9 - EXAMPLE OF WEBINAR PROMOTIONAL BANNER

■ 3.3.2 STANDARDS ACADEMY TRAININGS

In its objective of upskilling on standards-related topics, StandICT.eu 2026 also organised several online trainings via its Standards Academy²⁷. Details will be expanded upon in separate deliverable D4.2, however a brief overview is pertinent here due to these trainings' relationship to the project's general stakeholder engagement activities.

Similarly to Table 6, Table 7 provides an overview of the different organised trainings. In total, **6 trainings were organised by M17, with an aggregate of 591 registrations.**

Training	Date	Registrations
Towards the future of education on standardisation ²⁸	13 June 2023	47
Geopolitics of ICT standardisation ²⁹	29 January 2024	193
Standardisation in practice: When is the right time for standardisation in research processes? ³⁰	1 February 2024	48
Open Source &	18 March 2024	136

²⁷ <https://standict.eu/euos-academy>

²⁸ <https://www.standict.eu/index.php/events/webinar-euos-standards-academy-towards-future-education-standardisation>

²⁹ <https://www.standict.eu/index.php/events/standards-academy-webinar-geopolitics-ict-standardisation-29-january-2024>

³⁰ <https://www.standict.eu/index.php/events/standardisation-practice-when-right-time-standardisation-research-processes-01-february-2024>

Standardisation ³¹		
Insights from the European Standardisation Panel Survey ³²	21 May 2024	93
Geopolitics of ICT Standardisation: Focus on India ³³	27 May 2024	74

TABLE 7 - LIST OF STANDARDS ACADEMY TRAININGS BY M17

■ 3.3.3 SME LEADERSHIP WORKSHOPS

As laid out in Chapter 1, one of StandICT.eu 2026's core target audiences are SMEs. In that capacity, and in support of its comprehensive education strategy catering for a broad range of stakeholders (of which the Standards Academy Trainings presented above are an illustration of), a series of SME leadership workshops was also devised. The objective is to raise SMEs' interest and expertise towards leading Technical Committees or Working Groups of different SDOs. Two workshops are foreseen by the end of the project's tenure.

A first workshop was organised in November 2023, with 51 registrations. It was organised in synergy with Small Business Standards (SBS), the Annex III Organisation mandated by the European Commission to represent SMEs in European standardisation processes, during its annual Meeting Standards event³⁴. This was perceived as a strategic occasion to increase synergies between different stakeholders aiming towards the same objective.

Benefitting from StandICT.eu 2026's partnership with Small Business Standards (magnified in a Memorandum of Understanding), two SBS experts with leadership positions in Technical Committees participated in the workshop to share their tips and advice on how to better participate in standardisation work, and to engage in leadership positions (convenors, chairs, etc.). Table 8 synthesises this information in a table format, while Figure 10 displays the promotional banner that was used for dissemination purposes.

Beyond the alignment with SBS, the workshop also benefited from the prior contact made with the NGI Sargasso project³⁵. Due to the modalities under this specific project, a set of SMEs needed further upskilling in standardisation. The workshop was deemed very useful for them in follow up communications with the NGI Sargasso project manager.

The second iteration of this workshop is now due at M26 of the project. Following this successful introductory session, the second workshop will aim to go in more depth, with

³¹ <https://www.standict.eu/index.php/events/training-webinar-open-source-and-standardisation>

³² <https://www.standict.eu/index.php/events/euos-training-webinar-insights-european-standardisation-panel-survey>

³³ <https://www.standict.eu/events/geopolitics-ict-standardisation-focus-india>

³⁴ Meeting Standards is an annual week-long event organised by Small Business Standards, aimed at increasing awareness on standardisation issues for SMEs. More details on the overall event can be found at the [following link](#).

³⁵ [Link](#) to the NGI Sargasso website.

possible interactive and pragmatic exercises to reinforce the hard skill set of leadership implications in standardisation bodies' technical committees and working groups.

Workshop	Date	Registrations
Developing leadership capacity for SMEs in European and international SDOs	15 November 2023	51

TABLE 8 - LIST OF SME LEADERSHIP WORKSHOPS ORGANISED BY M17

FIGURE 10 - PROMOTIONAL BANNER FOR THE FIRST SME LEADERSHIP WORKSHOP

■ 3.3.4 THIRD-PARTY EVENTS

Beyond its own events, StandICT.eu 2026 also aims to participate in relevant third-party events. In other cases, even without formally participating as speakers, partners of the StandICT.eu 2026 consortium participated in third-party events as attendants, to maintain engagement levels in different stakeholder circles. Such events were also cross-referenced on StandICT.eu 2026's own platform, under its Events section.

Table 9 shows the different third-party events attended and cross-referenced for the benefit of other stakeholders by StandICT.eu 2026 members by M17. In total, StandICT.eu 2026 partners spoke at 5 third-party events, while further cross-referencing and attending 7 others.

Third-party Event	Organiser	Date & Location	Speaking slot (Y/N)
ETSI Research Conference: Maximising the	ETSI	6-8 February 2023 (Sophia Antipolis, France)	N

Impact of European 6G Research through Standardisation ³⁶			
Standardisation in the financial sector: Opportunities and Challenges ³⁷	INFINITECH	23 February 2023 (Online)	Y
Gender Responsive Standardisation: supporting gender equality through standards ³⁸	CEN-CENELEC	10 March 2023 (Online)	N
How to ensure the Digital Product Passport empowers SMEs ³⁹	Small Business Standards	21 June 2023 (Online)	N
EURAS Annual Standardisation Conference ⁴⁰	European Academy for Standardisation (EURAS)	28-30 June 2023 (Aachen, Germany)	Y
UNE Information Day: Digital Product Passport ⁴¹	UNE (Spanish Standardisation Body)	11 September 2023 (Online)	Y
Borderless Cyber Conference ⁴²	Borderless Cyber	11-12 September 2023 (London, United Kingdom)	N
INATBA Digital Blockchain Week ⁴³	INATBA	19-21 September 2023 (Brussels, Belgium)	N
ETSI Security	ETSI	16-19 October 2023 (Sophia Antipolis,	N

³⁶ <https://www.standict.eu/etsi-research-conference-6G>

³⁷ <https://www.standict.eu/fintech-standardisation-webinar>

³⁸ <https://www.standict.eu/gender-responsive-standardization>

³⁹ <https://www.standict.eu/events/how-ensure-digital-product-passport-empowers-smes-21062023>

⁴⁰ <https://www.standict.eu/euras-2023-standardisation>

⁴¹ <https://www.standict.eu/une-information-day-digital-product-passport>

⁴² <https://www.standict.eu/borderless-cyber-2023>

⁴³ <https://www.standict.eu/events/inatba-digital-blockchain-week-2023-192021-september-2023>

Conference ⁴⁴		France)	
AIOTI Workshop: Accelerating standardisation in the nexus of mobility, buildings and energy ⁴⁵	AIOTI	31 January 2024 (Brussels, Belgium)	Y
ETSI Artificial Intelligence Conference ⁴⁶	ETSI	5-7 February 2024 (Sophia Antipolis, France)	Y
INSTAR project: Shaping International Standards in Advanced ICT Tech Regulation ⁴⁷	INSTAR	19 April 2024 (Online)	N

TABLE 9 - LIST OF THIRD-PARTY EVENTS ATTENDED AND CROSS-REFERENCED BY M17

3.4 Communication Outreach

Fourth and last of StandICT.eu 2026's engagement channels are various communication outreach methods. These are essential in disseminating the project's main outputs and milestones to the widest possible audience – starting with the six main targeted stakeholder groups, but also importantly to the general public (SG7).

This outreach can be pinned down to three main strands:

- Social media, via Twitter, LinkedIn and Youtube;
- Publications and Reports, both self-published by the StandICT.eu 2026 consortia or cross-referenced from external sources for the benefit of the stakeholder community;
- Newsletters and Press Releases, to inform of capital milestones.

The three below subsections present each strand in more detail.

■ 3.4.1 SOCIAL MEDIA

⁴⁴ <https://www.standict.eu/etsi-security-conference-2023>

⁴⁵ <https://www.standict.eu/events/aioti-workshop-accelerating-standardisation-nexus-mobility-buildings-and-energy>

⁴⁶ <https://www.standict.eu/etsi-ai-conference>

⁴⁷ <https://www.standict.eu/events/instar-project-shaping-international-standards-advanced-ict-tech-regulation>

Social media plays a central part in communication outreach efforts. StandICT.eu 2026 has three main social media accounts:

- X (former Twitter): @Stand_ICT, with **1169 followers**;
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/standict-eu/>, with **1885 followers**;
- YouTube: @StandICTeu, with **44 subscribers**

These accounts leverage the work accomplished by the previous iterations of the StandICT.eu project. As such, they can count on important followers numbers. Figure 11 provides an overview of the number of followers on LinkedIn and X (formerly Twitter), and evolutions between M1 and M17 - testifying of the constant expansion of the StandICT.eu 2026 community.

FIGURE 11 - EVOLUTIONS IN NUMBER OF TWITTER AND LINKEDIN FOLLOWERS BETWEEN M1-M17

Going into more details, the StandICT.eu **LinkedIn page has 1885 followers coming from over 35 countries and 5 continents**. Since the last update in May 2023, **184 posts have been published that have collected 53095 impressions, 1723 likes, 1560 clicks, 319 reposts and 56 comments**. The posts that were most successful were those relating to the

promotion of technical reports, webinars (in particular those ones on Women in ICT Standardisation) and Open Calls.

As described by the graphics below (Figure 12), we collected 1667 overview page views (999 from desktop and 668 from mobile), 1876 total page views (1137 from desktop and 739 from mobile), 867 overview unique visitors (609 from desktop and 262 from mobile) and 878 total unique visitors (619 from desktop and 263 from mobile).

FIGURE 12 - LINKEDIN PAGE DATA

The StandICT.eu **Twitter** page has **1169 followers**. With **more than 240 tweets since the beginning of this edition**, the most successful ones are those relating to the promotion of technical reports and Commission initiatives, events (such as webinars and workshops) and Open Calls.

Last, regarding **Youtube**, **16 videos were produced and published** (for a total of **44 subscribers**).

Table 10 offers a summary of the social media KPIs.

Social media KPI	Target Value (M36)	Current Value (M17)
Social media content published (X - formerly Twitter)	>20 tweets/month	21.89
Social media content published (LinkedIn)	>10 posts/month	16.53

Followers on X, formerly Twitter	1500	1169
Followers on LinkedIn	3000	1885
Original videos produced and published	36	16

TABLE 10 - SUMMARY OF SOCIAL MEDIA KPIS AT M17

■ 3.4.2 PUBLICATIONS & REPORTS

StandICT.eu 2026 also engages with the broad stakeholder community via its different Publications and Reports. These can be of two main natures:

- Reports published by the StandICT.eu 2026 consortium **first handedly**. These can include deliverables of an external nature, such as research documents (eg, StandICT.eu Policy Paper: The Evolving ICT Standardisation Landscape⁴⁸) and also the Landscape Reports (expanded upon priorly in Section 3.2.3);
- Reports and useful information sources for ICT standardisation stakeholders cross-referenced from **external sources**. By M17, 16 such external reports were cross-references - and can be found under the 'Publications' section of the StandICT.eu 2026 platform⁴⁹. Some may be specifically addressed to a defined target audience, such as for SMEs (eg, an SME guide on Information Security Controls⁵⁰, or another one on Blockchain & DLT adoption for SMEs⁵¹). Such cross-referencing enables to create additional synergies in the ICT standardisation landscape, with StandICT.eu 2026 as a central focal point for a diverse community of stakeholders.

■ 3.4.3 NEWSLETTERS & PRESS RELEASES

Last, StandICT.eu 2026 outreaches out to its growing community via regular newsletters and press releases.

- By M17, **13 newsletters were issued, with a total number of 860 subscribers**. Newsletters generally focused on the opening of new Open Calls, or on newly released publications to disseminate to the StandICT.eu community. The full list can be found at the dedicated section of the platform⁵²;
- By M17, **16 press releases** were issued. These are published after the accomplishment of different project milestones, such as the signature of new Memorandums of Understandings with organisations (eg, a 12 December 2023 press release on the a new MoU with Drone4GREEN⁵³) or participation of the StandICT.eu

⁴⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/10037154>

⁴⁹ <https://www.standict.eu/publications>

⁵⁰ <https://www.standict.eu/sme-guide-security>

⁵¹ <https://www.standict.eu/sme-guide-blockchain-dlt>

⁵² <https://www.standict.eu/standict-newsletters>

⁵³ <https://www.standict.eu/news/press-release-standict-drones4green>

2026 consortia in important events (eg, participation in the European Commission's Multi Stakeholder Platform for ICT Standardisation of 21 March 2024⁵⁴). The full list of press releases can be found under the News section of the platform⁵⁵.

⁵⁴ <https://www.standict.eu/news/standicteu-joins-european-multistakeholder-platform-meeting-present-funding-opportunities>

⁵⁵ <https://www.standict.eu/news>

4. M17 ECOSYSTEM STATE OF PLAY

Chapter 4 depicts the state of play of the StandICT.eu 2026 ecosystem at the project's halfway course.

While four Open Calls took place by M17, final data for OC4 is not yet confirmed. However, up until OC3 **107 fellows** were funded. The **proportion of female fellows grew by 9 percentage points** from OC1, to 29.63%.

Regarding specific stakeholder categories, and the critical ones that were identified in Chapter 2, **225+ SMEs were directly engaged** into the StandICT.eu 2026 project, and a **further 1640+ were indirectly engaged** (notably via SME multipliers). **630+ academic and research community stakeholders** were also engaged, and **180+ stakeholders emanating from the open-source community**.

Additionally, **12 different European or international standardisation organisations and 6 NSBs were directly engaged**, as well as **policymakers from 3 core European Commission Directorate Generals** (DG CNECT, DG GROW, DG RTD). Last, **16 new collaborations were established with ICT standardisation-related Horizon Europe projects** (on top of 2 previous collaborations which were extended into StandICT.eu 2026), either through Memorandums of Understanding or cross-project cooperation and information sharing.

This Chapter goes through this data, expanding upon each important stakeholder category.

4.1 StandICT.eu 2026 Fellows

■ 4.1.1 DATA ON FUNDED FELLOWS ACROSS OPEN CALLS

Four Open Calls took place between M1 and M17. At time of writing, the official selection process results of Open Call 4 are still under confirmation - but data until Open Call 3 shows that **107 fellowships were funded, while an additional 104 applications were received for Open Call 4**.

Figure 13 shows a snapshot of the state of play across the first 3 Open Calls, while Figure 14 displays the data received for Open Call 4 applications (official results are, as expressed above, not yet available at time of writing). Further detailed information about the fellows can be found in D3.3. However, aggregated data depicts a vivid ecosystem, which maintains a high level of engagement throughout each Open Call. On average, over 100 applications were received for each Open Call. The applications are diverse, as is the composition of SDOs in which the funded fellows undertake their work.

FIGURE 13 - AGGREGATED DATA ON FELLOWSHIPS FROM OPEN CALL 1 TO OPEN CALL 3

FIGURE 14 - FELLOWSHIPS' DATA FOR OPEN CALL 4 APPLICATIONS

In order to better display the work being accomplished by the StandICT.eu 2026 fellows, a dedicated page was created on the project's website in the Spring of 2024⁵⁶. Each fellow can be identified with his or her picture, as well as the affiliation, country of origin and SDO in which the funded work is being accomplished. A small quote from the fellow is added at the end of each profile page, in order for external stakeholders to immediately understand the added-value of the work being conducted, and what it refers to. Figure 15 displays an example of such profile pages.

⁵⁶ <https://www.standict.eu/index.php/funded-fellows>

Pavel Cuchriajev

StandICT.eu Fellows / Pavel Cuchriajev

[LinkedIn](#) |

Full Name: Pavel Cuchriajev
Title & Organisation Name: [Technical expert contributor, Standard Norge](#)
Country: Lithuania

SDO: • [ISO/IEC](#)

Value of Research

"My fellowship significantly contributes to the ICT standards landscape by advancing the Biometric System-on-Card (BSoC) standards, particularly within the ISO/IEC 17839 series."

FIGURE 15 - EXAMPLE OF FUNDED FELLOW PROFILE PAGE

■ 4.1.2 ALIGNMENT WITH EU PRIORITIES

StandICT.eu 2026 strives to align the work of its funded fellows as closely as possible with defined European priorities. This is done through various synergies with European policymakers, of which further details will be outlined in upcoming Section 4.2.2.

However, relating to the impact of the funded fellows, the below data shows the extent to which the work carried out by the respective fellows in each call mirrored the priority areas of the European Commission's Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation⁵⁷. Updated annually, the plan lists all of the topics considered of critical importance where standardisation should play a central role in the implementation of the policy.

Each technology is encompassed under four main overarching meta-areas:

- Key Enablers & Security, **where 80 fellowships were recorded up to Open Call 3 and an additional 76 applications were received for Open Call 4** (under review);
- Societal Challenges, **where 1 fellowship was recorded up to Open Call 3 and an additional 6 applications were received for Open Call 4** (under review) ;
- Innovation for the Digital Single Market, **where 11 fellowships were recorded up to Open Call 3 and an additional 4 applications were received for Open Call 4** (under review);
- Sustainable Growth, **where 15 fellowships were recorded up to Open Call 3 and an additional 18 applications were received for Open Call 4** (under review).

■ 4.1.3 WOMEN EXPERTS

The percentage of women experts increased from Open Call 1 to Open Call 3 by 9 percentage points, and while the final data for Open Call 4 are still under review, **application numbers show an additional increase to 32.05%**. Table 11 shows this evolution.

⁵⁷ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation>

Open Call	Percentage of Female Fellows
OC1	20.69%
OC2	12.12%
OC3	29.63%
OC4 (applications)	32.05%

TABLE 11 - PROGRESSION IN THE PROPORTION OF FEMALE FELLOWS IN STANDICT.EU 2026 OPEN CALLS

While the overall percentage remains relatively low (20.22%), structural factors outside of the scope of the StandICT.eu 2026 should be taken into consideration. Such numbers unfortunately reflect a more general state of affairs in the digital sector in Europe - as demonstrated in a March 2023 study by the European Parliamentary Research Service⁵⁸.

Nonetheless, StandICT.eu 2026 took practical measures to attempt to play its part in addressing this situation. It organised two webinars on Women in Standards, respectively on 4th July 2023 and 7th March 2024⁵⁹. All-female panels were set up, to discuss the existing barriers for women in ICT standardisation, but also the main achievements that existed and could provide inspiration to other prospective female experts.

In both these webinars, considerable synergies were further built upon, with speakers coming from a variety of SDOs, other EU-funded projects, or companies. Figures 16 and 17 provide an overview of the speakers and their background.

Further ideas are now being considered to increase the impact of such webinars, as well as complementary modalities of engagement with female experts. A cross-project communication was initiated with the new Women TechEU project⁶⁰, to further promote ICT standardisation and the StandICT.eu 2026 Open Calls and trainings to its community of women entrepreneurs. More details on these specific events will be reported in D6.4.

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[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/ATAG/2023/739380/EPRS_ATA\(2023\)739380_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/ATAG/2023/739380/EPRS_ATA(2023)739380_EN.pdf)

⁵⁹ Refer to Chapter 3, and Section 3.3.1, for more details and registration levels.

⁶⁰ <https://womentecheuropa.eu/>

FIGURE 16 - PROMOTIONAL BANNER FOR WOMEN IN ICT STANDARDS 2 WEBINAR

FIGURE 17 - PROMOTIONAL BANNER FOR WOMEN IN ICT STANDARDS 3 WEBINAR

4.2 Established Synergies

■ 4.2.1 STANDARDS BODIES

As apparent in the data of the 4 Open Calls run by M17, StandICT.eu 2026 funded fellows are active in numerous standards bodies. On top of that, ties were more directly consolidated (or created) with some of them, via their participation in some of the project’s engagement channels presented in Chapter 3. This is particularly the case of National Standards Bodies, in which StandICT.eu 2026 Fellows are not directly supported, but where they may still be active and where additional, more direct synergies may also exist.

In total, StandICT.eu 2026 has funded fellowships across **12 different standardisation organisations**, and this number will expand with the forthcoming funding batches. Beyond, it has **also established synergies with 6 different National Standards Bodies**.

Table 12 offers a precise overview of these synergies⁶¹.

SDO		Number of Funded Fellowships (OC1-OC3) ⁶²	Other StandICT.eu 2026 Engagements
	CEN-CENELEC ⁶³	31	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Speaker slots (Andrea Caccia & Belen Suarez) - 15 November 2023 Workshop 'Developing leadership capacity for SMEs in European and international standardisation organisations' ❖ Speaker slot (Ben Kokx) - 7 March 2024 Webinar 'Open Source & the Cyber Resilience Act' ❖ Speaker slot (Mian Livia) - 21 May 2024 Standards Academy Training 'Insights from the European Standardisation Panel Survey' ❖ Cross-reference of CEN-CENELEC's FG Quantum Standardisation Roadmap & Report on Quantum Technologies Use Cases (30 March 2023) ❖ Member of FOREST Group (Philip Maurer - CEN-CENELEC Project Manager for RTD Collaboration) ❖ Interviewed expert in StandICT.eu 2026 Research Report ('Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape') (Ashok Ganesh)
	ETSI	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ StandICT.eu 2026 participation at ETSI AI Conference (5-7 February 2024) ❖ External Advisory Group & FOREST Group member (Lindsay Frost - Chairman of ETSI ISG CIM) ❖ Cross-reference of the ETSI Security Conference on StandICT.eu 2026 website (26 May 2023)

⁶¹ Mapped synergies here are high-level ones - and do not cover each of the funded fellow's activities in the different SDOs.

⁶² As explained previously, confirmed data is not yet available for Open Call 4 at time of writing.

⁶³ Including stand-alone participations in CEN.

	ISO/IEC ⁶⁴	42	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Speaker slots (Torbjörn Lahrin & Marius Preda) - 24 October 2023 Webinar 'Navigating the Citiverse' ❖ Speaker slots (Isabella de Michelis, Sandra Feliciano, Marzia Bolpagni, Paloma Llana & Lluïsa Marsa Llacuna) - 7 March 2024 Webinar 'Women in ICT Standardisation' ❖ Members of FOREST Group (Viveka Bonde - ISO/IEC SC42; Sandra Feliciano ISO/IEC JTC1/SC27-36-42)
	ITU	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Speaker slot (Pilar Orero) - 24 October 2023 Webinar 'Navigating the Citiverse' ❖ Speaker slot (Rim Belhassine-Cherif) - 7 March 2024 Webinar 'Women in ICT Standardisation'
	IETF	4	N/A
	IEEE	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Speaker slot (Adriana Nugter) - 29 February 2024 Webinar 'Open Source & the AI Act' ❖ StandICT.eu 2026 participation at IEEE COMPSAC 2023 (27-28 June 2023) ❖ Member of External Advisory Group (Silona Bonewald - Executive Director of IEEE SA OPEN) ❖ Interviewed expert in StandICT.eu 2026 Research Report ('Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape') (Konstantinos Karachalios)
	O-RAN Alliance	1	N/A
	3GPP	1	N/A

⁶⁴ Including stand-alone participations in both ISO and IEC.

	OASIS	0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Speaker slot (Jamie Clark) - 14 March 2024 Webinar 'Legal Challenges and Innovation for OSS and Standardisation Collaboration' ❖ Interviewed expert in StandICT.eu 2026 Research Report ('Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape') (Jamie Clark)
	DIN	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Speaker slot (Benjamin Helfritz) - 28 April 2023 Webinar 'Digital Product Passport' ❖ Speaker slot (Christian Goroncy) - 1 February 2024 Standards Academy Training 'Standardisation in practice: When is the right time for standardisation in research processes?' ❖ Speaker slot (Daniel Haack) - 18 March 2024 Standards Academy Training 'Open Source and Standardisation' ❖ Member of External Advisory Group (Stephan Weisgerber - DIN Head of Digital Platforms) ❖ Interviewed expert in StandICT.eu 2026 Research Report ('Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape') (Daniel Haack)
	UNE	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ StandICT.eu 2026 participation at the UNE Information Day on the Digital Product Passport (11 September 2023)
	Danish Standards	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Speaker slot (Annete Bogh) - 21 May 2024 Standards Academy Training 'Insights from the European Standardisation Panel Survey'
	Austrian Standards	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Member of External Advisory Group (Karl Gruen - Director Austrian Standards)

	National Standards Authority of Ireland	N/A	❖ Member of FOREST Group (Dave Lewis - NSAI Mirror committee on AI)
	BSI	N/A	❖ Member of FOREST Group (Panos Kudumakis - Head of UK Delegation to ISO/IEC JTC1/SC29)

TABLE 12 - ESTABLISHED SYNERGIES WITH STANDARDS BODIES BY M17

■ 4.2.2 POLICYMAKERS

As laid out in Chapter 2, serving broader European interests is the key goal of the four-fold sequence of StandICT.eu 2026's ecosystem building approach. In that regard, links with policymakers are crucial. Up to now, StandICT.eu 2026 has directly interacted with several policymakers from **3 core Directorate Generals of the European Commission**, especially via its participation in Multi-Stakeholder Platform on ICT Standardisation meetings, different StandICT.eu webinars, or other European events and meetings.

The project has consolidated many of the links it had developed over the first iterations of StandICT.eu. It is in close contact with DG CNECT officers, namely Carlos Lopes Rodriguez, Emilio Davila Gonzalez, and Paul Killeen (CNECT D3). Many of the directions taken by the project over these first 18 months, notably discussions around the finality and outputs of the FOREST group, were taken throughout regular calls. The StandICT.eu 2026 consortium was also present at two meetings of the Multi Stakeholder Platform on ICT Standardisation (MSP - September 2023 & March 2024), with official representation and presentations of the project by Trust-IT, complemented by the presence of partners Open Forum Europe, DIGITAL SME, and Fraunhofer.

However, StandICT.eu 2026 was also able to considerably expand its ties to DG GROW's own standardisation initiatives. Namely, it was able to follow the activities of the High-Level Forum on Standardisation (HLF), launched in January 2023, through participation in it by consortium partner DIGITAL SME. The latter is actively operational in 5 of the workstreams, as well as represented in the high-level Sherpa meetings. StandICT.eu 2026 standards education activities were notably presented in the framework of the Workstream 1 on Standards Education, co-chaired by TU Eindhoven and CEN-CENELEC - and will further be highlighted in the upcoming Conference on Standards Education, organised under the umbrella of the High-Level Forum on Standardisation⁶⁵. StandICT.eu 2026 involvement in AI standardisation

⁶⁵ <https://www.aanmelder.nl/hlf-edu/home>

was also brought up in the framework of a workshop organised under the auspices of Workstream 4 on Alignment between European and International Standards.

Last, a large number of European policymakers (mainly from DG CNECT, but also DG GROW and DG RTD) were invited as speakers in StandICT.eu 2026 events - testifying of the vividness of the ties. Table 13 gives a synthesis of all these established synergies.

European Commission DG	StandICT.eu 2026 Engagement
DG CNECT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Project officers (CNECT D3) - regular exchanges ❖ StandICT.eu 2026 participation in MSP ❖ Speaker slot (Ilias Iakovidis) - Webinar 'Digital Product Passport' (28 April 2023) ❖ Speaker slot (Carlos Lopez Rodriguez) - Standards Academy Training 'Towards the future of education on standardisation' (13 June 2023) ❖ Speaker slot (Cristina Martinez) - Webinar 'Navigating the Citiverse' (24 October 2023) ❖ Speaker slot (Emilio Davila Gonzales) - Webinar 'OFE Lounge Series: Kick-off' (22 February 2024) ❖ Speaker slot (Antoine-Alexandre André) - Webinar 'OFE Lounge Series: AI Act' (29 February 2024) ❖ Speaker slot (Filipe Jones Mourao) - Webinar 'OFE Lounge Series: Cyber Resilience Act' (7 March 2024)
DG GROW	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ StandICT.eu 2026 participation in HLF via partner DIGITAL SME ❖ Speaker slot (Eszter Batta) - Webinar 'Women in ICT Standardisation' (7 March 2024)
DG RTD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Speaker slot (Gergely Tardos) - Standards Academy Training 'Towards the future of education on standardisation' (13 June 2023) ❖ Speaker slot (Gergely Tardos) - Standards Academy Training 'Insights from the European Standardisation Panel Survey' (21 May 2024)

TABLE 13 - ESTABLISHED SYNERGIES WITH POLICYMAKERS BY M17

■ 4.2.3 SMES & INDUSTRY

Industrial players, and in particular SMEs, were given particular attention in these first 17 months. In total, **225+ individuals from SMEs directly joined the StandICT.eu ecosystem**, covering funded fellowships for SMEs (29), and participants to different StandICT.eu events and trainings. While this number is likely to be higher in practice (and omits fellowship data from Open Call 4, with application results still under validation), precise profiling of every registration has not been possible for every event until this stage. It is something the project consortium aims to work on in the second half of the project, and which is further developed upon in the final Chapter of this deliverable. In addition, via tailored mailings of StandICT.eu 2026 partner DIGITAL SME to its SME community, **1640+ SME contacts** (individual companies but also national and regional associations, acting as multipliers) were regularly outreached to inform about StandICT.eu 2026 milestones.

Synergies with the industry were found both through relationships and actions with direct companies, and through industry associations. This materialised essentially through participation of some of the latter to the EAG and FOREST, contributions to certain Landscape Reports, to StandICT.eu 2026's Research Report on 'Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape' (D2.1) and participation in events (**117 identified registrants from large companies**).

In addition to these more transversal engagement channels, additional effort was put on engaging with the SME community. The StandICT.eu 2026 project was presented 3 times in DIGITAL SME and Small Business Standards' joint Working Group on Standards (May 2023; September 2023; May 2024) - a **50+ group composed** of both SME ICT standardisation experts working in different Technical Committees, as well as other SMEs interested in ICT standardisation topics. In May 2024, a consultation process was also conducted on StandICT.eu 2026's Research Report 'Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape' (D2.1) - through an oral discussion, complemented by written feedback. The aim was to ensure that SME views were properly encompassed in the final version of the report, due at a later stage of the project.

Throughout each Open Call, specific dissemination channels were used to outreach to the SME community. This occurred through tailored large mailings, and the use of DIGITAL SME's CRM (Customer Relationship Manager) to tailor the information to its specific audiences interested in ICT standardisation, as well as through social media outreach. Figure 18 shows a snapshot of one of the outreach mailings. For each mailing, **between 1640 and 1670 recipients were outreached to** (some of them being multipliers such as the 30 national and regional associations across Europe which compose DIGITAL SME's membership, and not individual companies, bringing the overall total number to a larger amount) - complemented by multiplication and further dissemination on social media.

FIGURE 18 - SNAPSHOT OF A MAILING EXAMPLE FOR THE SME COMMUNITY

In addition, a new SME section⁶⁶ was created on the StandICT.eu 2026 website. The page presents the main activities designed for increasing SME engagement into the project. Namely, an SME Mentorship Programme was launched for Open Call 4. The goal of the programme is to walk newcomers SME experts who benefit from StandICT.eu 2026 support to benefit from the advice and guidance of more experienced StandICT.eu fellows. This is designed as both a pull lever for SME prospective applicants, to have the assurance that they will be guided in their activities, and to engage more with the rest of the StandICT.eu 2026 community of funded fellows. As such, it is an important new means of stakeholder engagement.

Under Open Call 4, 54 individuals applied as mentors, and 22 as mentees. This testifies of considerable engagement and interest around the programme, considering the option to apply as either of the two was only optional. At time of writing, the process is ongoing to matchmake the different applicants (whether mentors or mentees), based on similar topical interest. An information session is then planned to kick-start the process, and further monitor it.

The SME page of the website also includes testimonials from SMEs that have benefitted from StandICT.eu 2026 support. This process enabled to get in touch with specific companies, and to get to know more about their take on participation in ICT standardisation. It is also a means to get further SMEs engaged into ICT standardisation, taking inspiration from the work of others who followed the same path.

Last, SME engagement was also achieved through various events - some of which were tailored to the SME community's needs, such as the SME leadership workshop of 15 November 2023⁶⁷, organised in synergy with Small Business Standards.

Table 14 gives an overview of the different synergies established with SMEs and other industry players - separating the two to give a clearer perception of the specific SME dimension. In total, **127+ industry associations or larger companies** were directly engaged into the project, **while 225+ SMEs were directly engaged too.**

Industrial actor	StandICT.eu 2026 Engagement
-------------------------	------------------------------------

⁶⁶ <https://www.standict.eu/supporting-smes>

⁶⁷ <https://standict.eu/meeting-standards-workshop>

type	
Industry associations & larger companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ EAG Membership (Sandra Drechsler - VDMA) ❖ EAG Membership (Sebastian Hallensbelen - VDE) ❖ EAG Membership (Ana Garcia Robles - BDVA) ❖ Speaker slot (Brian McAuliffe - HP) - Standards Academy Training 'Towards the future of education on standardisation' (13 June 2023) ❖ Speaker slot (Dirk Weiler - Nokia) - Standards Academy Training 'Geopolitics of ICT standardisation' (29 January 2024) ❖ Interviewee in D2.1 (Jimmy Ahlberg - Ericsson) ❖ Interviewee in D2.1 (Debora Comparin - Thales) ❖ Interviewee in D2.1 (Michael Eslamian - Huawei) ❖ Interviewee in D2.1 (Jochen Friedrich - IBM) ❖ Interviewee in D2.1 (Dirk Weiler - Nokia) ❖ 117 identified registrants from large companies in StandICT.eu 2026 events
SMEs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ 29 SME funded fellows (until OC3) ❖ DIGITAL SME regular outreach to its membership about StandICT.eu 2026 activities ❖ Presentation of StandICT.eu 2026 activities in 3 DIGITAL SME-SBS Working Group meetings (50+ members) ❖ Memorandums of Understanding with Small Business Standards and SMEunited - consulted in the stakeholder consultation process on StandICT.eu 2026 D2.1 (May 2024) ❖ SME Mentorship Programme (April 2024) ❖ New SME section on StandICT.eu 2026 platform (April 2024) ❖ Organisation of Standards Academy Workshop 'Developing leadership capacity for SMEs in SDOs' - SME speakers & attendance (November 2023) ❖ Speaker slots (Susanne Guth-Orlowski - Spherity & Thomas Rödning - Narravero) - Webinar 'Digital Product Passport' (28 April 2023) ❖ Speaker slot (Emilia Tantar - BlackSwan) - Webinar 'Women in ICT Standards' (4 July 2023) ❖ Speaker slot (Antonio Kung - Trialog) - Webinar 'Navigating the Citiverse' (24 October 2023) ❖ Speaker slot (Isabella De Michelis - ErnieApp Ltd) - Webinar 'Women in ICT Standardisation' (7 March 2024) ❖ 141 identified registrants from SMEs in StandICT.eu 2026 events

TABLE 14 - ESTABLISHED SYNERGIES WITH INDUSTRY & SMES BY M17

■ 4.2.4 RESEARCH & ACADEMIA

Similarly to the SME community, outreaching to Research & Academia was a key objective of StandICT.eu 2026's stakeholder engagement activities. In total, approximately **630+ members of the research and academic community were engaged into the StandICT.eu 2026 ecosystem**, especially via the funded fellowships (30 fellowships coming from Academia/Research) and delivered trainings.

This essentially happened through the work of the project's Standards Academy, and the leadership of project partner Fraunhofer. Different training materials were devised⁶⁸, and then further presented to stakeholders. At time of writing, 6 trainings were carried out. Such trainings were both delivered *for* the benefit of the research community, but also *with* academia's direct contribution to it. Each training built on different synergies with academic centres, universities, think-tanks or field experts - facilitating both the quality of the trainings, and also the latter's dissemination to relevant audiences.

Table 15 provides an overview of these different trainings, and the academic stakeholders that were engaged in the process. **In total, 600+ people were engaged into the below listed trainings by M17, across 6 separate sessions** and either as speakers or attendants. In addition, StandICT.eu 2026's External Advisory Group benefits from the presence of Sandra Feliciano (Polytechnic Institute of Porto) – and 30 funded fellows come from academic institutions.

Standards Academy Training	Academic Stakeholders Synergies
'Towards the future of education on standardisation' (13 June 2023)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Technical University Berlin ❖ University of Belgrade ⇒ 47 engaged registrants
'Geopolitics of ICT standardisation' (29 January 2024)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Technical University Berlin ❖ Yonsei University ❖ Humboldt Universität zu Berlin ❖ Berlin Contemporary China Network ⇒ 193 engaged registrants
'Standardisation in practice: When is the right time for standardisation in research processes?' (1 February 2024)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Technical University Berlin ❖ University of Belgrade ❖ HS Boosterµ ⇒ 48 engaged registrants
'Open Source and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Technical University Berlin

⁶⁸ <https://www.standict.eu/euos-training-academy>

Standardisation' (18 March 2024)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Policy & Industry Experts ⇒ 136 engaged registrants
'Insights from the European Standardisation Panel Survey' (21 May 2024)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Technical University Berlin ❖ HS Booster ⇒ 93 engaged registrants
'Geopolitics of ICT Standardisation - Focus on India' (27 May 2024)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Technical University Berlin ❖ Policy & Industry Experts ⇒ 74 engaged registrants

TABLE 15 - ESTABLISHED SYNERGIES WITH RESEARCH & ACADEMIA BY M17

StandICT.eu 2026 will further reinforce links with European research and academia and promote their participation in international standardisation and application to the project's open calls. One of the next immediate steps in this direction is the decision to organise the project's M18 interim impact event as a workshop within the scope of the upcoming EURAS⁶⁹ conference, which will be held in Delft (Netherlands) from 19 to 21 June 2024.

■ 4.2.5 OPEN-SOURCE COMMUNITY

During the first half of the project, StandICT.eu 2026 has reached out to **180+ individuals from the open-source community**.

Ties to the open-source community were overseen through the presence in the StandICT.eu 2026 consortia of Open Forum Europe (OFE). Beyond dissemination of the project's main outputs and developments through OFE's organisation, two main channels were used to engage on a broader level:

- StandICT.eu 2026's Research Report on Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape (D2.1). Finalised in May 2024, it built on a series of interviews with 30 high-level experts in the field across 2023 and early 2024. Among the interviewees, **8 were tied to organisations linked to the open-source community**. Beyond the interviews themselves, the Report goes into depth into the dynamics behind open source and standardisation - with a series of preliminary recommendations to be further discussed among stakeholders⁷⁰;
- The OFE Lounge Event Series: 'Standardisation and Open Source in the Age of Software Regulation'⁷¹, organised under the StandICT.eu 2026 umbrella between 22 February 2024 and 3 April 2024. Throughout 5 different sessions, it enabled to engage

⁶⁹ <https://www.euras.org/>

⁷⁰ At time of writing, the Report is not published yet and is under consultation with a wide range of stakeholders, in order to receive further input.

⁷¹ <https://openforumeurope.org/event/ofe-lounge-2024-standardisation-and-open-source-in-the-age-of-software-regulation/>

with a wide **variety of stakeholders active in the open-source community, totalling 172 registrations.**

Table 16 summarises the main established ties.

Engagement Channel	Established Synergies with the Open-Source Community
Interviews D2.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Mirko Boehm (Linux Foundation Europe) ❖ Silona Bonewald (Leadingbit Solutions LLC) ❖ Deborah Bryant (Open Source Initiative) ❖ Jamie Clark (OASIS Open) ❖ Jochen Friedrich (IBM) ❖ Tobie Langel (UnlockOpen) ❖ Arnaud Le Hors (IBM) ❖ Dirk-Willem van Gulik (Apache Software Foundation)
OFE Lounge Event Series	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Mirko Boehm (Linux Foundation Europe) ❖ Jochen Friedrich (IBM) ❖ Mike Milinkovich (Eclipse Foundation) ❖ Jamie Clark (OASIS Open) ❖ Dirk-Willem van Gulik (Apache Software Foundation) <p>⇒ 172 engaged registrants</p>

TABLE 16 - ESTABLISHED SYNERGIES WITH THE OPEN-SOURCE COMMUNITY BY M17

■ 4.2.6 EUROPEAN PROJECTS

StandICT.eu collaborates directly **with 18 EU-funded projects** that contribute to ICT standardisation at European and international levels. **Out of these 18, 16 new collaborations were established with Horizon Europe projects under StandICT.eu 2026.** Most of them are materialised through a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU), while some others lie on sole cross-project communication and joint ad-hoc activities.

All the established MoUs were also individually outreached in the framework of StandICT.eu 2026's Stakeholder Consultation Process⁷² of the May 2024 Research Report 'Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape' (D2.1).

Collaborations with the SPATIAL and COGITO projects were established under StandICT.eu 2023 and reconducted under StandICT.eu 2026. Table 17 highlights the new synergies achieved under StandICT.eu 2026: **11 new MoUs, and 5 additional cross-project cooperations.**

⁷² More information on the Consultation Process was provided in Chapter 3, Section 3.2.5.

Project		Nature of relation	Project Area	Specific Engagement Activities
	ReIncarnate	MoU	Digital transformation of construction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Information sharing - notably on Open Calls ❖ Outreached as part of the Stakeholder Consultation Process of D2.1
	HumanTech	MoU	Digital transformation of construction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Information sharing - notably on Open Calls ❖ Outreached as part of the Stakeholder Consultation Process of D2.1
	Stand4EU	MoU	Manufacturing standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Information sharing - notably on Open Calls ❖ Outreached as part of the Stakeholder Consultation Process of D2.1 ❖ Speaker slot (Olga Meyer) - Webinar 'Women in ICT Standardisation' (4 July 2023)
	CORTEX2	MoU	Metaverse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Information sharing - notably on Open Calls ❖ Outreached as part of the Stakeholder Consultation Process of D2.1
	NGI Sargasso	MoU	Future Internet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Information sharing - notably on Open Calls ❖ Outreached as part of the Stakeholder Consultation Process of D2.1 ❖ Standards Academy Workshop: 'Developing leadership skills for SMEs in SDOs' (15 November 2023) - Alignment calls to better disseminate the information and attract SMEs from the NGI

				Sargasso project
	Team Aware	MoU	Emergency Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Information sharing - notably on Open Calls ❖ Outreached as part of the Stakeholder Consultation Process of D2.1
	CyberSEAS	MoU	Cybersecurity of smart grids	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Information sharing - notably on Open Calls ❖ Outreached as part of the Stakeholder Consultation Process of D2.1
	6G-Predict	MoU	6G Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Information sharing - notably on Open Calls ❖ Outreached as part of the Stakeholder Consultation Process of D2.1
	Drones4GREEN	MoU	Unmanned Aerial Vehicles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Information sharing - notably on Open Calls ❖ Outreached as part of the Stakeholder Consultation Process of D2.1
	HSBooster	Cross-project cooperation	R&I and standardisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Information sharing - notably on Open Calls ❖ Outreached as part of the Stakeholder Consultation Process of D2.1 ❖ Joint Webinar - 'Standardisation in practice: When is the right time for standardisation in research processes?' (1 February 2024) ❖ Speaker slot (Sandra Feliciano - Webinar 'Women in ICT Standardisation' (7 March 2024)

 EXA4MIND	EXA4Mind	MoU	Big Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Information sharing - notably on Open Calls ❖ Outreached as part of the Stakeholder Consultation Process of D2.1
 SUNRISE	SUNRISE	Cross-project cooperation	Critical communications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Information sharing - notably on Open Calls ❖ Outreached as part of the Stakeholder Consultation Process of D2.1
 BLOCK STAND	BlockStand	MoU	Blockchain standardisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Information sharing - notably on Open Calls ❖ Outreached as part of the Stakeholder Consultation Process of D2.1 ❖ Speaker slot (Luïsa Marsal) - Webinar 'Women in ICT Standardisation' (7 March 2024)
 pq-react	PQ React	Cross-project cooperation	Quantum Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Information sharing - notably on Open Calls ❖ Outreached as part of the Stakeholder Consultation Process of D2.1
 EDU4Standards.eu	Edu4Standards	Cross-project cooperation	Standards education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Information sharing - notably on Open Calls ❖ Alignment on Standards Academy initiatives
 WOMEN TechEU	Women Tech EU	Cross-project cooperation	ICT gender gap	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Information sharing - notably on Open Calls

TABLE 17 - ESTABLISHED SYNERGIES WITH OTHER EU-FUNDED PROJECTS BY M17

5. LESSONS LEARNT & NEXT STEPS

The StandICT.eu 2026 community has considerably expanded across the first half of the project's course. Building from the work done throughout the first two iterations of the project, it was able to further extend its links with three specific stakeholder groups identified as critical from the start of the project: SMEs (**225+ directly engaged stakeholders, and 1640+ indirectly and via other SME multipliers**), the academic and research community (**630+**), and the open-source community (**180+**).

Additionally, **12 different European or international standardisation organisations and 6 NSBs were directly engaged** with, as well as **policymakers from 3 core European Commission Directorate Generals**. Last, **16 new collaborations were established with ICT standardisation-related Horizon Europe projects**, either through Memorandums of Understanding or cross-project cooperation and information sharing.

Overall, **with 53500 users having visited its website between M1-M17**, StandICT.eu 2026 is clearly established as the cornerstone platform for ICT standardisation in Europe - and for all types of stakeholders. Figure 19 synthesises StandICT.eu 2026's stakeholder engagement approach into one condensed visual, linking stakeholder groups to engagement channels and final key outputs by M17.

FIGURE 19 - STANDICT.EU 2026 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT SYNTHESIS (M17)

As the consortia now looks on to the second half of the project’s tenure, some lessons can be made. Registrants for StandICT.eu 2026 events, for instance, could be better profiled and such information fields made mandatory in order to better understand where they are coming from. This is currently under process, with the creation of a new database compiling all of the registrants over all of the project’s different events, with a more fine-tuned profiling of each registrant. At time of writing, 1104 contacts were collated in this new StandICT.eu 2026 community database, of which 538 have declared their affiliation to organisations. Figure 20 displays this allocation - also showcasing that, among this overall sum, SMEs represent 30% of established contacts, and Academia & Research stakeholders 31%.

One of the aims is now to increase this proportion of clearly identifiable stakeholders. Figure 21 shows a geographical representation of these contacts identified in the new database by M17. Germany, Spain, Belgium and France are the countries featuring the highest number of engaged individuals. By M36, the project consortium plans that such numbers are risen further more, and across new countries.

FIGURE 20 - GEOGRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF THE ENGAGED STANDICT.EU 2026 COMMUNITY IN THE NEW DATABASE BY M17

FIGURE 21 - ALLOCATION PER STAKEHOLDER TYPE OF THE ENGAGED STANDICT.EU COMMUNITY IN THE NEW DATABASE BY M17